

Functional coupling between Piezo1 and TRPM4 influences the electrical activity of HL-1 atrial myocytes

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Abstract The transient receptor potential melastatin 4 (TRPM4) channel contributes extensively to cardiac electrical activity, especially cardiomyocyte action potential formation. Mechanical stretch can induce changes in heart rate and rhythm, and the mechanosensitive channel Piezo1 is expressed in many cell types within the myocardium. Our previous study showed that TRPM4 and Piezo1 are closely co-localized in the t-tubules of ventricular cardiomyocytes and contribute

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to the Ca^{2+} -dependent signalling cascade that underlies hypertrophy in response to mechanical pressure overload. However, there was no direct evidence showing that Piezo1 activation was related to TRPM4 activation *in situ*. In the present study, we employed the HL-1 mouse atrial myocyte-like cell line as an *in vitro* model to investigate whether Piezo1–TRPM4 coupling can affect action potential properties. We used the small molecule Piezo1 agonist, Yoda1, as a surrogate for mechanical stretch to activate Piezo1 and detected the action potential changes in HL-1 cells using FluoVolt, a fluorescent voltage sensitive dye. Our results demonstrate that Yoda1-induced activation of Piezo1 changes the action potential frequency in HL-1 cells. This change in action potential frequency is reduced by Piezo1 knockdown using small interfering RNA. Importantly knockdown or pharmacological inhibition of TRPM4 significantly affected the degree to which Yoda1-evoked Piezo1 activation influenced action potential frequency. Thus, the present study provides *in vitro* evidence of a functional coupling between Piezo1 and TRPM4 in a cardiomyocyte-like cell line. The coupling of a mechanosensitive Ca^{2+} permeable channel and a Ca^{2+} -activated TRP channel probably represents a ubiquitous model for the role of TRP channels in mechanosensory transduction.

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Abstract figure legend Piezo1–TRPM4 interaction influences the action potential frequency of HL-1 atrial myocytes. Top: Yoda1-evoked Piezo1 activation stimulates TRPM4 via the increase of intracellular Ca^{2+} . This activation of TRPM4 depolarizes plasma membrane through Na^+ entry and induces further Ca^{2+} influx through other Ca^{2+} transporters and/or channels. In HL-1 cells, this results in an increase of action potential frequency. Bottom: inhibition of TRPM4 in HL-1 cells affects the degree to which Piezo1 activation changes action potential frequency. This finding provides *in vitro* evidence of a probably universal model in mechanosensory pathways: a Ca^{2+} -activated ion channel acts as a downstream effector or amplifier of a primary Ca^{2+} -permeable mechanosensor. Created with [BioRender.com](https://www.biorender.com).

Key points

- The transient receptor potential melastatin 4 (TRPM4) and Piezo1 channels have been confirmed to contribute to the Ca^{2+} -dependent signalling cascade that underlies cardiac hypertrophy in response to mechanical pressure overload. However, there was no direct evidence showing that Piezo1 activation was related to TRPM4 activation *in situ*.
- We employed the HL-1 mouse atrial myocyte-like cell line as an *in vitro* model to investigate the effect of Piezo1–TRPM4 coupling on cardiac electrical properties.
- The results show that both pharmacological and genetic inhibition of TRPM4 significantly affected the degree to which Piezo1 activation influenced action potential frequency in HL-1 cells.
- Our findings provide *in vitro* evidence of a functional coupling between Piezo1 and TRPM4 in a cardiomyocyte-like cell line.
- The coupling of a mechanosensitive Ca^{2+} permeable channel and a Ca^{2+} -activated TRP channel probably represents a ubiquitous model for the role of TRP channels in mechanosensory transduction in various (patho)physiological processes.

Yang Guo completed his PhD in Medicine at the University of New South Wales, Australia. Since his PhD training, he has been continuously working on the role of mechanosensitive ion channels in cardiac remodelling, in the Mechanosensory Biophysics Laboratory of the Victor Chang Cardiac Research Institute, Australia. His work aims to develop potential novel therapeutic targets for prevention of heart diseases such as pathological cardiac hypertrophy.

Introduction

The Ca^{2+} -activated transient receptor potential melastatin 4 (TRPM4) channel (Launay et al., 2002) contributes extensively to cardiac physiological and pathological processes because of its involvement in Ca^{2+} -dependent signalling (Guinamard et al., 2004, 2006, 2015; Hof et al., 2019; Mathar et al., 2014; Wang et al., 2018; Watanabe et al., 2008). Previous studies have identified that TRPM4 contributes to the electrical and structural remodelling in the sinoatrial node (SAN), atria and ventricles (Demion et al., 2007, 2014; Guinamard et al., 2015; Hedon et al., 2021; Hof et al., 2013, 2016; Hu et al., 2017; Mathar et al., 2014; Simard et al., 2013, 2021; Vandewiele et al., 2022). In addition, it is also considered a key protein involved in the underlying mechanisms of cardiac hypertrophy and heart failure (Frede et al., 2020; Gueffier et al., 2017; Guo et al., 2021; Hedon et al., 2021; Jacobs et al., 2015; Kecskes et al., 2015).

It is known that acute mechanical stretch on cardiac cells including the pacemaker cells, atrial cardiomyocytes and ventricular cardiomyocytes can induce changes in heart rate and rhythm (Kohl et al., 1999; Quinn & Kohl, 2021). Because TRPM4 has been shown to be insensitive to membrane stretch (Constantine et al., 2016; Nikolaev et al., 2019), it probably functions as a 'mechano-effector' (Hamill & Maroto, 2007) or a signal amplifier (Nikolaev et al., 2019), which requires its association with other mechanosensitive channels acting as the primary transducers of mechanical forces into Ca^{2+} signals. The mechanosensitive channel Piezo1 (Coste et al., 2010) has emerged as a key sensor of mechanical forces within the cardiovascular system (Beech & Kalli, 2019; Coste et al., 2010; Douguet et al., 2019). Recently, Piezo1 has also been implicated in mechanosensitive processes within the heart (Jiang et al., 2021; Yu et al., 2022). Our previous study has shown that TRPM4 and Piezo1 are closely co-localized in t-tubules of ventricular cardiomyocytes and contribute to the hypertrophic signalling transmission in response to mechanical pressure overload, involving a Ca^{2+} -dependent pathway (Yu et al., 2022). Piezo1 is probably the upstream mechanosensor whose activation can drive TRPM4 channel gating. This Piezo1–TRPM4 interaction may contribute to the cardiac mechano-electric coupling that occurs in settings of acute mechanical stretch. However, there was previously no direct evidence showing that Piezo1 activation is associated with TRPM4 activation *in situ*.

In the present study, the HL-1 mouse atrial myocyte-like cell line (Claycomb et al., 1998) was employed as an *in vitro* model to investigate whether Piezo1 activation can further activate TRPM4 channels to affect action potential properties. We used Yoda1 (Syeda et al., 2015) as a surrogate for mechanical stretch to activate Piezo1 and detected the action potential

changes in HL-1 cells using FluoVolt, a fluorescent voltage sensitive dye. Our results demonstrate that not only does Piezo1 activation change action potential generation in HL-1 cells, but also that inhibition of TRPM4 in HL-1 cells significantly affects the degree to which Yoda1-evoked Piezo1 activation changes action potential frequency. Thus, the present study provides *in vitro* evidence of a Piezo1–TRPM4 functional coupling in a cardiomyocyte-like cell line.

Methods

Ethical approval

The mouse experiments at the Victor Chang Cardiac Research Institute, Australia, were approved by the Animal Ethics Committee of Garvan/St Vincent's (Approval number 20-06; AU) in accordance with the guidelines of both the Australian code for the care and use of animals for scientific purposes (8th edition, National Health and Medical Research Council, AU, 2013) and the Guide for the Care and Use of Laboratory Animals (8th edition, National Research Council, USA, 2011). The rabbit experiments were performed at the Institute for Experimental Cardiovascular Medicine, University Heart Centre Freiburg – Bad Krozingen, and Faculty of Medicine, University of Freiburg, Germany, in accordance with the guidelines stated in directive 2010/63/EU of the European parliament on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes and were approved by the local authorities in Baden-Württemberg (X-16/10R).

Animals

The mice used in the present study were all male C57BL/6J wild-type in the age range 11–13 weeks, originally from Australian BioResources (Moss Vale, NSW, Australia). The New Zealand white rabbits used in experiments were all male and approximately 10 weeks old, weighing ~1700 g, originally from Charles River Laboratories (Wilmington, MA, USA).

Cell culture

The HL-1 cells were a kind gift from Dr Richard Harvey (Victor Chang Cardiac Research Institute, Darlinghurst, NSW, USA) and were cultured using an optimized protocol from the Claycomb Laboratory (Claycomb et al., 1998). The cells were maintained at 37°C with 5% CO_2 in a special culture medium mixture composed of 87% Claycomb Medium (Sigma-Aldrich, St Louis, MO, USA), 10% fetal bovine serum (FBS) (Sigma-Aldrich), 1% penicillin-streptomycin (stock: 10 000 units of penicillin and 10 mg of streptomycin mL^{-1}) (Sigma-Aldrich), 1%

norepinephrine (stock: 10 mM, Sigma-Aldrich) and 1% L-glutamine (Stock: 200 mM, Sigma-Aldrich). The cells were split or harvested after they reached more than 90% confluency using TrypLE (Thermo Fisher Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA). HEK293T *Piezo1*^{-/-} cells were a kind gift from Dr Ardem Patapoutian (Scripps, San Diego, CA, USA) and were maintained at 37°C with 5% CO₂ in Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium with high glucose (DMEM) (Sigma-Aldrich) supplemented with 10% FBS.

Adult mouse atrial and ventricular cardiomyocytes isolation and purification

All the mice were heparinized and then killed by cervical dislocation following the Animal Research Act 1985 No 123 (New South Wales, Australia). As previously described (Guo et al., 2021; Yu et al., 2022), each dissected mouse heart was perfused through the aorta and the coronary arteries with 10 mL of perfusion buffer (pH 7.2) for 5 min at 37°C with a Langendorff apparatus. The perfusion buffer contains 135 mM NaCl, 4 mM KCl, 1 mM MgCl₂, 0.33 mM NaH₂PO₄, 10 mM Hepes, 10 mM glucose, 10 mM 2,3-butanedione monoxime (BDM) and 5 mM taurine. Following that, the heart was perfused for 15 min at 37°C with 30 mL of digestion buffer composed of the above perfusion buffer and collagenase B, D (for both, dose by body weight: 0.4 mg g⁻¹; Roche, Basel, Switzerland) and protease enzyme type XIV (dose by body weight: 0.06 mg g⁻¹; Sigma-Aldrich). After the perfusion, the heart was placed into a pH 7.4 transfer buffer containing 135 mM NaCl, 4 mM KCl, 1 mM MgCl₂, 0.33 mM NaH₂PO₄, 10 mM Hepes, 5.5 mM glucose, 10 mM BDM and 5 mg mL⁻¹ bovine serum albumin (BSA). The muscles of the atria and ventricles were separated then torn into small pieces and gently dispensed into the transfer buffer repeatedly with a pipette to isolate atrial and ventricular cardiomyocytes respectively. Next, the cell suspension was filtered using a 200 μm Falcon cup filter (BD Pharmingen, Franklin Lakes, NJ, USA) and centrifuged at 20 g for 2 min. After the isolation, the atrial and ventricular cardiomyocytes were purified following a protocol developed by Nicks et al. (2022). The purified cardiomyocytes were frozen immediately in liquid nitrogen and stored at -80°C for subsequent experiments.

Adult mouse cardiac fibroblast isolation and primary culture

Mouse cardiac fibroblasts were isolated from four adult mice and primary cultured using a protocol optimized from the protocols of University of Virginia (2013) and Zeigler et al. (2016). Mouse ventricles were rinsed with Krebs Henseleit Buffer (Sigma-Aldrich), minced

into ~1 mm pieces, then digested using Liberase enzyme (Roche). Successive digestions were centrifuged for 10 min at 400 g then the cells were seeded into 100 mm cell culture dishes in DMEM (Sigma-Aldrich) supplemented with 10% FBS (Sigma-Aldrich) and 1% penicillin-streptomycin (stock: 10 000 units of penicillin and 10 mg of streptomycin mL⁻¹, Sigma-Aldrich). After 7 days of primary culture at 37°C and 5% CO₂, the fibroblasts were rinsed with phosphate-buffered saline (PBS) and collected for subsequent experiments.

Small interfering RNA (siRNA) transfection

HL-1 cells from a confluent culture were dissociated using TrypLE (Thermo Fisher Scientific), then seeded in cell culture plates with Claycomb medium mixture (described previously). After 5 h, the medium mixture was replaced by a serum- and antibiotic-free culture medium mixture overnight (16 h). After that, the cells were placed in normal Claycomb medium mixture again, at which time the cells reached ~50% confluency. siRNA against *Trpm4* (70 nM; catalog. no. MSS229248; Invitrogen, Carlsbad, CA, USA) or *Piezo1* (70 nM; catalog. no. s107969 and s107970, 1:1 mixture; Invitrogen) were transfected for corresponding gene knockdown. In addition, two non-targeting siRNAs, Stealth RNAi siRNA Negative Control (70 nM; catalog. no. 452001; Invitrogen) and Silencer Negative Control No. 1 siRNA (70 nM; catalog. no. 4390843; Invitrogen) were transfected as negative control for *Trpm4* and *Piezo1* knockdown, respectively. siRNA was transfected using Lipofectamine RNAiMAX Transfection Reagent (Invitrogen) diluted in Opti-MEM transfection medium (Invitrogen) for 24 h at 37°C with 5% CO₂ in accordance with the manufacturer's instructions. The cells were used for further experiments after additional 48 h of culture.

Quantitative reverse transcriptase PCR (qRT-PCR)

Piezo1, *Trpm4* and *Cacna1c* gene expression in the present study was determined by a qRT-PCR. Total RNA was extracted from mouse atrial and ventricular cardiomyocytes, mouse cardiac fibroblasts and HL-1 cells, using the RNeasy Fibrous Tissue Mini Kit (Qiagen, Hilden, Germany). cDNA was synthesized from total RNA (500 ng) using the SuperScript III First-Strand Synthesis SuperMix kit (Invitrogen). qRT-PCR was performed with the CFX384 Touch Real-Time PCR Detection System (Bio-Rad, Hercules, CA, USA), PCR master mix Light-Cycler 480 SYBR Green I Master (Invitrogen) and mouse RT-PCR primer sets (Sigma-Aldrich, USA): *Trpm4* sense GAGAAGCCCACAGATGCCTATG, *Trpm4* anti-sense AGCACCGACACCACCAAGTTTG; *Piezo1* sense CTA TGAGCCACTGTTACCAT, *Piezo1* anti-sense CTGCA

TGGCTAGTGGATAGG; *Cacna1c* sense TGACTACC TGACTAGGGATTGGTCTA, *Cacna1c* anti-sense TGCT CTAGGTTCCCTTCTGTTTTG; and GAPDH sense TATGTCGTGGAGTCTACTGG, GAPDH anti-sense AGTGATGGCATGGACTGTGG. Samples were run in technical triplicate and the mRNA expression levels were normalized to those of GAPDH to calculate relative gene expression using the $\Delta\Delta C_t$ method.

Western blotting

For total protein extraction, isolated mouse atrial cardiomyocytes, ventricular cardiomyocytes, cardiac fibroblasts and HL-1 cells were lysed in a lysis buffer (pH 7.4) containing 150 mM NaCl, 50 mM Tris-HCL, 1% Triton X-100, 1 mM sodium orthovanadate, 1 mM beta-glycerophosphate, 5 mM dithiothreitol and Mini-Complete protease inhibitors (Roche). Then, 40 μg of protein was loaded on 4%–20% Mini-PROTEAN TGX Gels (Bio-Rad) and separated by electrophoresis. Samples were then transferred to polyvinylidene fluoride membranes (Bio-Rad), blocked with 5% BSA then incubated overnight with primary anti-TRPM4 (dilution 1:200; RRID: AB_2040250; catalog. no. ACC-044; Alomone Labs, Jerusalem, Israel) or anti-GAPDH (dilution 1:10 000; RRID: AB_561053; catalog. no. 2118; Cell Signaling Technology, Danvers, MA, USA) antibody. Next, horseradish peroxidase-conjugated goat anti-rabbit secondary antibody (dilution 1:10 000; RRID: AB_955447; catalog. no. ab6721; Abcam, Cambridge, UK) and Amersham ECL Western blotting detection reagents (GE Healthcare, Chicago, IL, USA) were used for immunological detection as previously described (Guo et al., 2021). Protein levels were quantified by densitometry using FIJI, version 1.53t (National Institutes of Health, Bethesda, MD, USA).

HL-1 cell action potential and Ca^{2+} transient measurements

HL-1 cells in a 96 well plate were rinsed with DMEM supplemented with 10% FBS (both from Sigma-Aldrich). For action potential detection, the cells were incubated with a fluorescent voltage sensitive dye FluoVolt (dilution 1:500; Invitrogen) in the Claycomb medium mixture described previously but without penicillin-streptomycin, at 37°C with 5% CO_2 for 45 min. For Ca^{2+} transient detection, the cells were incubated with 2 μM Fluo-4 AM (Invitrogen), a fluorescent Ca^{2+} indicator, in the penicillin-streptomycin-free Claycomb medium mixture at 37°C with 5% CO_2 for 30 min. After that, the cells were rinsed twice with the DMEM mixture and then kept in the penicillin-streptomycin-free Claycomb medium mixture during the experiment. HL-1 cell membrane potential and Ca^{2+} transient data acquisition was carried out on an Eclipse Ti2-E Inverted Optical Mapping epifluorescence

microscope (Nikon Instruments, Tokyo, Japan), using a 20 \times objective lens and 2 \times 2 binning. The recording interval was 5 or 10 ms for different experiments. In the central area of the imaging region of interest (ROI), a 40 \times 40 μm ROI which contains approximate 4–6 cells was used for data analysis for each well. The recorded HL-1 membrane potential data or Ca^{2+} transient data was initially analysed using the build-in NIS-Elements Microscope Imaging Software, version 5.11.03 (Nikon Instruments) to extract the intensity profile over time. After that, in-house MATLAB (Mathworks, Natick, MA, USA)-based data analysis software (authors: Anton Shpak and Satya Arjunan from the Innovation Centre, Victor Chang Cardiac Research Institute, Australia) was used to measure the HL-1 cell action potentials or Ca^{2+} transients and to calculate parameters including the frequency, duration, amplitude and maximum upstroke velocity, etc. The baseline rundown of intensity as a result of the sample bleaching under the microscope was also corrected using this software. In the final data analysis, the action potential duration at 90% repolarization (APD90) was analysed as an alternative to the actual action potential duration to avoid potential recognition errors caused by background noise.

Experimental procedure for drug addition and imaging for HL-1 cells

First, the cells in each well in a 96 well plate were imaged for 10 s. Then drug was added to the well. After that, the cells were imaged for another 10 s. The data before and after drug addition was compared to identify the drug effect. In each well, the cells were kept in 100 μL of penicillin-streptomycin-free Claycomb medium mixture. Then, 33.3 μL of the medium mixture containing the corresponding drug was added into the well to reach the final concentration needed for experiment. This method of drug addition helps to achieve a balance between increasing the diffusion rate of the drug and reducing the impact of liquid volume increase to the cells. For pharmacological inhibition experiments, HL-1 cells were incubated with flufenamic acid (20 or 40 μM) or 9-phenanthrol (20 or 40 μM), together with FluoVolt (Invitrogen), respectively. Nifedipine (catalog. no. N7634), lidocaine (catalog. no. L7757), flufenamic acid (catalog. no. F9005), 9-phenanthrol (catalog. no. 211 281) and NS 1619 (catalog. no. N170) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Yoda1 (catalog. no. 5586) was purchased from Tocris Bioscience (Bristol, UK).

Rabbit tissue preparation and measurements

All rabbits were killed according to a previously described protocol (Greiner et al., 2022). Briefly, anaesthesia and euthanasia were performed via i.m. injection of esketamine hydrochloride (Ketanest S 25 mg mL^{-1} ; Pfizer

Pharma PFE GmbH, Berlin, Germany; 12.5 mg kg⁻¹ body weight)/xylazine hydrochloride; Rompun 2%, Bayer Vital GmbH, Leverkusen, Germany; 0.2 mL kg⁻¹ body weight) and i.v. injection of esketamine hydrochloride/thiopental (Thiopental Inresa 0.5 g; Inresa Arzneimittel GmbH, Freiburg, Germany; 12.5 mg mL⁻¹), respectively, and until apnoea. The right atrium was excised during Langendorff perfusion and then stored in modified Tyrode's solution at 4°C. The SAN and the crista terminalis (CT) were isolated and dissected into chunks by cutting perpendicularly to the CT. The resulting SAN-CT samples were glued (Histoacryl; B. Braun, Melsungen, Germany) to polyester plastic triangles (InVitroSys GmbH, Gräfelfing, Germany) and mounted on calibrated springs allowing detection of force of contraction (Fischer et al., 2019). The tissue was immersed in 2 mL of warm culture medium supplemented with 30 mM BDM (Sigma-Aldrich) with minimum preload to the holding wires of biomimetic culture chambers (InVitroSys GmbH). The whole assembly was then placed in a standard cell culture incubator (37°C, 5% CO₂). After 15 min of adaptation to the culture conditions, the BDM-containing medium was replaced with culture medium. After 15 min of further equilibration, the preload was adjusted to 1 mN.

After 2 h of adaptation to the final culture settings, 20 μM Yoda1 (catalog. no. SML1558; Sigma-Aldrich) was added directly to the culture chamber. Contractions were recorded during 15 min of incubation time. After this, 300 nM isoproterenol (catalog. no. I6504; Sigma-Aldrich) was added to the chamber to check for SAN-CT responsiveness.

Frequency data were analysed using a custom-made MATLAB (Mathworks) script based on the commercially available script from InVitroSys GmbH.

Electrophysiology

HL1 cells were plated on four 10 mm round coverslips at 25 000 cells per coverslip for patch clamp analysis. For the inside-out and the cell-attached configuration, the pipette solution was 140 mM NaCl, 2 mM CaCl₂, 2 mM MgCl₂, 3 mM KCl and 10 mM Hepes (pH 7.2) adjusted with NaOH. The extracellular solution relevant to electrophysiological recordings in Figs 1 and 6 contained: 90 mM KCl, 50 mM K aspartate, 3 mM NaCl, 2 mM MgCl₂, 10 mM glucose and 10 mM Hepes (pH 7.2), adjusted with KOH. The extracellular solution relevant to electrophysiological recordings in Fig. 5 contained: 140 mM NaCl, 2 mM MgCl₂, 3 mM KCl, 10 mM glucose and 10 mM Hepes (pH 7.2), adjusted with NaOH, with or without supplementation with 2 mM CaCl₂. Negative pressure was applied to patch pipettes using a High-Speed Pressure Clamp-1 (ALA Scientific Instruments, East Farmingdale, NY, USA) and recorded in millimetres of mercury (mmHg) using a piezoelectric pressure

transducer (World Precision Instruments, Sarasota, FL, USA). Borosilicate glass pipettes (Sigma-Aldrich) were pulled with a vertical pipette puller (PP-83; Narishige Scientific Instrument Lab, Tokyo, Japan) to produce electrodes with a resistance of 2.1–2.6 MΩ. The currents were amplified using an AxoPatch 200B amplifier (Axon Instruments, Scottsdale, AZ, USA), and data were sampled at a rate of 10 kHz with 1 kHz filtration and analysed using pCLAMP10 software (Axon Instruments). Representative cell-attached traces from HL-1 cells are shown with subsequent off-line filtering at 250 Hz. For 9-phenanthrol experiments, HEK293T Piezo1^{-/-} cells transfected with Piezo1 were pre-treated for 30 min with 50 μM 9-phenanthrol and cell-attached recordings of Piezo1 were carried out with or without the addition of 9-phenanthrol. Unitary conductance of pressure-evoked currents was calculated using the slope of the current–voltage plot where single channel amplitudes were measured in the cell-attached configuration at five separate holding potentials.

Immunofluorescence analyses

HL-1 cells were cultured in a 96 well plate (catalog. no. 6005182; PerkinElmer, Waltham, MA, USA) then fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde in PBS for 20 min at room temperature. The cells were then permeabilized with 0.1% Triton X-100 in 3% BSA in PBS for 2.5 min and blocked with 3% BSA in PBS for 1 h at room temperature. The cells were incubated with anti-connexin43 (dilution 1:500; RRID: AB_297 976; catalog. no. ab11370; Abcam) and anti-caveolin3 (dilution 1:500; RRID: AB_397 801; catalog. no. 610 421; BD Biosciences, San Jose, CA, USA) primary antibodies in the blocking solution overnight at 4°C. Secondary antibodies here, a goat anti-rabbit AF488 (dilution 1:500; RRID: AB_2 576 217; catalog. no. A-11 034; Thermo Fisher Scientific) and a goat anti-mouse AF647 (dilution 1:500; RRID: AB_2 811 129; catalog. no. ab150119; Abcam) were diluted in the same buffer and incubated with the cells for 1 h at room temperature. The nuclei were labelled with 4',6-diamidino-2-phenylindole (DAPI) (catalog. no. D9542; Sigma-Aldrich). The cells from each condition were imaged on a confocal microscope (LSM900; Zeiss, Oberkochen, Germany) using a 40× oil objective. Z-stacks were taken starting from the bottom of the cells for a total of 6 μm (12 × 550 nm) to include the entire height of the cell layer. For the purpose of analysis, imaging conditions were kept the same for all conditions. Statistical analyses were performed on maximum projection images from the image stacks using FIJI, version 1.53t (National Institutes of Health). Integrated fluorescence densities were measured from manual tracing along the cell membrane of 49–54 cells from three cultures per condition.

Statistical analysis

All averaged data are presented as the mean \pm SD. The statistical analysis was conducted using Prism, version 9.4.0 (GraphPad Software Inc., San Diego, CA, USA). For comparisons between two sets of data, paired (before–after drug addition in the same group) or unpaired (between different groups) Student's *t* test (two-tailed) was used to determine the statistical significance. One-way analysis of variance was used for comparisons among multiple data sets, followed by Tukey's *post hoc* test. $P < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. Individual *P* values are stated where appropriate.

Results

Characteristics of HL-1 cells

The *Piezo1* and *Trpm4* mRNA expression levels in HL-1 cells were examined by qPCR (Fig. 1A and B), in comparison with other mouse cardiac cells. The *Piezo1* mRNA expression level in HL-1 cells is 0.88-fold that in isolated adult mouse atrial cardiomyocytes, 3.52-fold that in mouse ventricular cardiomyocytes, and 0.22-fold that in primary adult mouse cardiac fibroblasts (Fig. 1A). The *Trpm4* mRNA expression level in HL-1 cells is 2.16-fold that in isolated adult mouse atrial cardiomyocytes, 7.51-fold that in mouse ventricular cardiomyocytes, and 2.82-fold that in primary adult mouse cardiac fibroblasts (Fig. 1B).

To confirm the presence of functional *Piezo1* channels, we monitored the Ca^{2+} levels of individual HL-1 cells in response to Yoda1 addition (Fig. 1C and D). The average fluorescence intensity of cells loaded with the intensimetric Ca^{2+} dye Fluo-4 remained the same after the addition of a dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) control (Fig. 1E) but started to rise after Yoda1 addition (final concentration = 2 μM) (Fig. 1F). An exemplar trace of a single HL-1 cell is shown in Fig. 1G. To additionally confirm the presence of stretch-activated *Piezo1* currents, we used patch clamp electrophysiology. The application of negative hydrostatic pressure (−30 mmHg) generated the opening of Ca^{2+} -permeable cation channels with a characteristic conductance of 35.7 ± 2.6 pS ($n = 4$) (Fig. 1H–J). In combination with the Yoda1-induced Ca^{2+} transients, this supports the presence of functional *Piezo1* channels in HL-1 cell membranes.

As the Ca^{2+} level increases, an action potential-like Ca^{2+} oscillation emerges post Yoda1 addition. To understand the influence of Yoda1 and *Piezo1* on action potential generation in HL-1 cells, we sought first to understand the mechanisms that drive action potentials in HL-1 cells and to generate reproducible culture conditions for HL-1 cell monolayers to probe these effects. To

Table 1. Control HL-1 cell initial spontaneous action potentials (ISAP) by cell seeding density and culture time.

Cell culture protocol	Seeding cell number per well (96 well plate)	Culture time (h)
No ISAP	25 000	72
Slow ISAP	24 000	96
Fast ISAP	40 000	72
	40 000	96
	50 000	72

understand the mechanisms that drive action potential generation in HL-1 cells, we made use of the L-type Ca^{2+} channel blocker nifedipine and the Na^{+} channel blocker lidocaine. We analysed action potential based on cell membrane potential imaging obtained in HL-1 cells (Fig. 2A). The addition of nifedipine did not exhibit a significant effect on action potential frequency at concentrations of 1, 2 and 10 nM (Fig. 2B). At 50 nM, the action potential was blocked in 60% ($P = 0.004$) of the wells in a 96 well plate; at 100 nM, the action potential was completely blocked ($P < 0.001$) in all the wells (Fig. 2B). The IC_{50} of nifedipine is 2–8 nM (at the lower end) for $\text{Ca}_{v1.2}$, a major molecular contributor the cardiac L-type Ca^{2+} channel current (Perez-Vizcaino et al., 1993; Pignier & Potreau, 2000). Therefore, the ability of nifedipine to block HL-1 action potentials was found at a concentration ~ 10 -fold the IC_{50} and was 100% effective when at a concentration average of 20-fold the IC_{50} . By contrast, with lidocaine at concentrations of 25, 50, 100, 250, 500 and 1000 μM , HL-1 cells still exhibited action potentials (Fig. 2C). Because the IC_{50} of lidocaine is 50 μM for the main cardiac Na^{+} channel $\text{Na}_{v1.5}$ (Nuss et al., 1995), the action potential was unaffected at concentrations of 10- and 20-fold the IC_{50} . These results suggest that the L-type Ca^{2+} channel is the main contributor of the action potential in HL-1 cells.

We found that the initial spontaneous action potential (ISAP) frequency of confluent HL-1 cells was strongly dependent on the cell culture conditions. In the present study, the HL-1 cells used in experiments were classified based on their synchronous ISAP frequency. The frequency was successfully controlled using different cell culture protocols to adjust cell seeding density and culture time (Table 1). There were no ISAP exhibited when seeding 25 000 cells per well in a 96 well plate for 72 h at 37°C with 5% CO_2 . By seeding 24 000 cells per well for 96 h or 40 000 cells for 72 h, all the cells exhibited a 'slow' ISAP, which is less than 20 transients in 10 s (Fig. 2D). This was significantly different ($P < 0.001$) than when 40 000 cells per well for 96 h or 50 000 cells for 72 h were seeded. In these cases, HL-1 cells in 94% of the wells (61/65 wells)

Figure 1. Gene expression levels and presence of functional Piezo1 channels in HL-1 cells

Piezo1 **A**, and *Trpm4* **B**, mRNA expression levels in HL-1 cells, mouse atrial cardiomyocytes (ACM), ventricular cardiomyocytes (VCM) and cardiac fibroblasts (CF). Results are presented as the mean \pm SD ($n = 3-6$ per group). n represents the number of separate culture dishes for HL-1 cells or the number of mice for mouse ACMs, VCMs and CFs. **C** and **D**, acquired individual HL-1 cell intracellular Ca^{2+} recordings using Fluo-4 AM 1 s before **C**, and 10 s after **D**, Yoda1 addition (final concentration = 2 μM). Scale bar = 50 μm . Fluorescence intensity ranges are represented using rainbow gradients. Fluo-4 fluorescence intensity change in HL-1 cells with DMSO addition **E**, and Yoda1 addition **F**. Results are presented as the mean \pm SD ($n = 18$ individual cells from three different wells in a 96 well plate). **G**, representative one individual cell data from **F**. Exemplar cell-attached recordings from HL-1 cells at 0 mmHg **H**, and -30 mmHg **I**. O1 and O2 represent the opening of two channels. **J**, quantification of the increase in open probability (P_o) of stretch activated channels recorded in HL-1 cells recorded at pipette potential (V_p) of +70 mV ($n = 4$ individual cells).

exhibited a ‘fast’ ISAP, which we classified as no less than 20 transients in 10 s (Fig. 2D). Therefore, the HL-1 cells used in the present study were classified into ‘No ISAP’ (AP number/10 s = 0), ‘Slow ISAP’ (AP number/10 s < 20) and ‘Fast ISAP’ (AP number/10 s > 20) groups. There was

no significant difference ($P = 0.978$) in the conduction velocity of HL-1 cells between the Slow ISAP group and the Fast ISAP group (Fig. 2E).

Figure 2F–H are representative confocal images of HL-1 cells from No ISAP, Slow ISAP and Fast ISAP

Figure 2. Characterization of action potential generation in HL-1 cells
 A, acquired HL-1 cell membrane potential image using FluoVolt. Scale bar = 50 μm . Fluorescence intensity range is represented using rainbow gradient. Nifedipine B, and C, lidocaine affect HL-1 cell action potential (AP). Results are presented as before-after drug addition. The final concentrations of nifedipine and lidocaine after addition are indicated. AP frequency is presented as AP numbers in 10 s ($n = 4-8$ per group). D, HL-1 cell initial spontaneous AP frequency by Slow and Fast ISAP cell culture protocols. Frequency is presented as AP numbers in 10 s. $n = 324$ in Slow ISAP group; $n = 65$ in Fast ISAP group. Results are presented as scatter plots with the mean \pm SD. E, conduction velocity of HL-1 cells in Slow and Fast ISAP groups ($n = 48$ in Slow ISAP group; $n = 24$ in Fast ISAP group). Results are presented as scatter plots with the mean \pm SD. n represents the number of wells in a 96 well plate in B, to E. Representative images of HL-1 cells from No ISAP F, Slow ISAP G, and Fast ISAP H, groups stained with the Connexin 43 (Cx43, green) and Caveolin 3 (red) antibodies as well as DAPI (blue). Arrows indicate the location of Cx43. Scale bar = 10 μm in all. I, representative image showing the integrated fluorescence density of Cx43 (green) on the cell membrane. J, quantitative data of integrated fluorescence densities of Cx43 in No, Slow and Fast ISAP groups ($n = 49-54$ per group). n represents the number of individual cells. Results are presented as scatter plots with the mean \pm SD.

groups, labelled with the anti-connexin 43 (Cx43, green) and anti-caveolin3 (red) antibodies and DAPI (blue). The integrated fluorescence density of Cx43 on the cell membrane as shown in Fig. 2I was quantitatively analysed in all three groups. The Cx43 expression levels are significantly different in the three groups ($P < 0.001$) and are increasing sequentially from No ISAP to Slow ISAP ($P = 0.045$) and Fast ISAP group ($P = 0.035$) (Fig. 2J).

In the present study, we mainly focused on the Slow ISAP group because its action potential frequency range is similar to the original report from Claycomb (2001). However, to provide a complete and comprehensive picture of the electrical activity seen in HL-1 cells we also show data from NO ISAP and FAST ISAP groups.

Piezo1 knockdown affects Yoda1-induced action potential frequency changes

To elucidate whether the Yoda-evoked responses present in Fig. 1 were Piezo1-dependent, we used siRNA mediated knockdown of Piezo1. The *Piezo1* mRNA expression levels were reduced by 68% ($P < 0.001$) in the *Piezo1*-targeting siRNA-treated cells compared to

the control siRNA-treated cells. (Fig. 3A). However, we were unable to detect the Piezo1 protein expression levels in HL-1 cells because no reliable antibody for mouse Piezo1 protein is commercially available. For validation of the gene knockdown, no significant difference was found in the *Cacna1c* ($P = 0.068$) and *Trpm4* ($P = 0.081$) mRNA expression levels between the *Piezo1*-targeting siRNA-treated cells and the control cells (Fig. 3B and C). There was no significant difference ($P = 0.576$) in the TRPM4 protein expression levels between the *Piezo1*-targeting siRNA-treated cells and the control cells (Fig. 3D and E).

We analysed the action potential numbers in 10 s (AP number per 10 s) as a measure of action potential rate; in addition, we analysed APD 90 and maximum upstroke velocity as parameters of action potential shape. In Slow ISAP cells from both the control siRNA-treated group (Fig. 4A) and the *Piezo1*-targeting siRNA-treated group (Fig. 4B), Yoda1 addition (final concentration = $2 \mu\text{M}$) induced a significant increase in the action potential frequency ($P < 0.001$) (Fig. 4B–D). However, the frequency in the *Piezo1*-targeting siRNA-treated group was 21.3% lower ($P < 0.001$) than that in the control

Figure 3. Validation of the *Piezo1* gene knockdown

Relative *Piezo1* A, *Cacna1c* B, and *Trpm4* C, mRNA expression in HL-1 cells treated with *Piezo1*-targeting siRNA (*siPiezo1*) or its control siRNA (*siCTL*) ($n = 4$ per group). D, Western blots showing TRPM4 protein expression in HL-1 cells treated with *siCTL* or *siPiezo1*. E, TRPM4 protein expression quantitative data normalized by GAPDH. Fold change was calculated relative to *siCTL* group ($n = 5$ per group). In all panels, quantitative results are presented as scatter plots with the mean \pm SD. Fold change was calculated relative to corresponding *siCTL* group. n represents the number of separate culture dishes.

Figure 4. Effects of Piezo1 knockdown on action potentials in Slow ISAP cells

A and B, representative action potential (AP) traces before and after Yoda1 addition (final concentration = 2 μ M) in siCTL (A) or siPiezo1 (A) treated HL-1 cells. AP frequency C, APD90 D, and AP maximum upstroke velocity E,

compared between siCTL-treated and siPiezo1-treated group. Results are presented as before-after drug addition. AP frequency ratio (*F*), APD90 ratio (*G*) and maximum upstroke velocity (*H*) calculated by after/before drug addition. Results are presented as scatter plots with the mean \pm SD ($n = 12-28$ per group with DMSO addition; $n = 32-33$ per group with Yoda1 addition). n represents the number of wells in a 96 well plate.

group after Yoda1 addition (Fig. 4A–C). DMSO addition did not show any significant effect on any of the three parameters (Fig. 4C–E). To quantify this further we looked at the action potential frequency and compared the frequency after addition to before addition, we refer to this as the after/before ratio. Accordingly, the after/before addition ratio was significantly higher ($P < 0.001$) with Yoda1 compared to DMSO in both groups, but the after/before ratio in the Piezo1-targeting siRNA-treated group was 32.6% lower ($P < 0.001$) than that in the control group (Fig. 4F). Yoda1 addition significantly increased the APD90 in both groups ($P < 0.001$). In the Piezo1-targeting siRNA-treated group, the APD90 was found to be higher ($P < 0.001$) than that in the control group after Yoda1 addition (Fig. 4D). The after/before ratio with Yoda1 addition was significantly higher ($P < 0.001$) than that with DMSO in both groups (Fig. 4G). However, there was no significant difference ($P = 0.143$) between the two groups with Yoda1 addition (Fig. 4G).

A significant decrease ($P < 0.001$) in maximum upstroke velocity was found after Yoda1 addition in both

groups, but no significant difference ($P = 0.785$) was found between the two groups (Fig. 4E). Yoda1 after/before ratio was significantly lower than DMSO after/before ratio, in both the Piezo1-targeting siRNA-treated group ($P < 0.001$) and the control group ($P < 0.001$), but no significant difference ($P = 0.070$) was found between the two groups in the Yoda1 after/before ratio (Fig. 4H).

Pharmacological inhibition of TRPM4 affects Yoda1 induced changes in action potential frequency

To test whether functional TRPM4 channels were present in HL-1 cells we used patch clamp electrophysiology. We saw little to no channel activity at rest ($n = 6$) in the cell attached configuration. On excision into a Ca^{2+} free extracellular solution, we did not observe an increase in channel activity when compared to the cell-attached configuration (Fig. 5A). By contrast, on excision into recording buffer containing 1 mM Ca^{2+} , we observed a noticeable inward cation current (26.86 ± 4.15 pA; $n = 6$) (Fig. 5B). This current was almost completely

Figure 5. TRPM4-like currents in inside-out patches from HL-1 cells

A, exemplar cell-attached to inside-out (*i/o*) recordings from HL-1 cells with a Ca^{2+} free extracellular solution. The time point of excision is labelled with an arrow and was recorded at a pipette potential (V_p) of +60 mV. B, exemplar cell-attached to inside-out (*i/o*) recordings from HL-1 cells with a Ca^{2+} containing extracellular solution (1 mM). The time point of excision is labelled with an arrow and was recorded at a pipette potential (V_p) of +60 mV. Also indicated with an arrow is the time point of addition of the TRPM4 blocker flufenamic acid (FFA). C, quantification of peak currents elicited in inside-out patches from control (CTL) conditions with Ca^{2+} in the extracellular recording solution compared to peak currents elicited in Ca^{2+} free ($-\text{Ca}^{2+}$) extracellular recording solution and when FFA was perfused onto the cytoplasmic face of the channel ($n = 6-8$ individual cells per group).

inhibited by perfusion of the TRPM4 blocker flufenamic acid (50 μM) (Fig. 5B and C). Thus, HL-1 cells exhibited a Ca^{2+} activated flufenamic acid sensitive cation current consistent with TRPM4.

With HL-1 cells in confluent cultures, DMSO addition had no effect in all groups. In No ISAP cells, Yoda1 addition (final concentration = 2 μM) activated a synchronous action potential in the control group, flufenamic acid (20 and 40 μM)-treated groups and 9-phenanthrol (20 μM)-treated group (Fig. 6A). However, with 20 μM 9-phenanthrol treatment, cells from 31.3% of the wells did not respond to Yoda1 addition ($P < 0.001$) (Fig. 6A). Furthermore, with 40 μM 9-phenanthrol, no

action potential was generated after Yoda1 addition (Fig. 6A). This is considered the potential blocking effect of 9-phenanthrol on Ca^{2+} channels, possibly including Piezo1. As further confirmation, we pre-treated HEK293T cells expressing Piezo1 with and without 9-phenanthrol. The stretch-activated Piezo1 currents in HEK293T cells also appeared to be inhibited ($P < 0.001$) by 50 μM 9-phenanthrol when pre-treated in this way (Fig. 6B and C). Moreover, in the HL-1 cells incubated with 40 μM 9-phenanthrol, the average fluorescence intensity of Ca^{2+} imaging remained the same level after Yoda1 addition (final concentration = 2 μM) (Fig. 6D). Therefore, 9-phenanthrol was excluded in subsequent experiments.

Figure 6. Flufenamic acid and 9-phenanthrol effect on No ISAP HL-1 cells
 A, HL-1 cells were pre-treated with flufenamic acid (FFA) or 9-phenanthrol (9-Phe), except the control groups (CTL). Action potential (AP) frequency is presented as AP numbers in 10 s. Results are shown as before-after DMSO/Yoda1 addition ($n = 4-10$ per group with DMSO addition; $n = 9-32$ per group with Yoda1 addition). n represents the number of wells in a 96 well plate. B, exemplar cell-attached recordings from HEK293T Piezo1^{-/-} cells expressing Piezo1-1591-GFP untreated control (CTL) (left) and pre-treated with 50 μM 9-Phe (right). C, quantification of peak currents elicited in cell-attached patches from HEK293T Piezo1^{-/-} cells expressing Piezo1-1591-GFP untreated control and pre-treated with 50 μM 9-Phe ($n = 10-12$ individual cells per group). D, Fluo-4 fluorescence intensity change in HL-1 cells with Yoda1 addition after pre-treatment with 40 μM 9-phenanthrol. Results are presented as the mean \pm SD ($n = 18$ individual cells from three wells in a 96 well plate).

Notably, in the 20 and 40 μM flufenamic acid-treated group, the action potential frequency after Yoda1 addition were 29.9% ($P = 0.014$) and 33.5% ($P = 0.014$) lower compared to the control group, respectively (Fig. 6A).

In Slow ISAP cells, Yoda1 addition (final concentration = 2 μM) induced a significant increase ($P < 0.001$) in action potential frequency in both control (Fig. 7A) and flufenamic acid-treated groups (Fig. 7B). In addition, the frequency in the flufenamic acid-treated group was 18.8% lower ($P < 0.001$) than that in the control group after Yoda1 addition (Fig. 7A–C). When calculated as the after/before drug addition ratio, the ratio with Yoda1 addition is significantly higher than that with DMSO addition in both groups, but the after/before ratio with Yoda1 addition in the flufenamic acid-treated group was 35.1% lower ($P < 0.001$) than that in the control group (Fig. 7F). There was a significant increase ($P < 0.001$) in APD90 after Yoda1 addition in both control and flufenamic acid-treated groups, but no significant difference ($P = 0.145$) between the two groups (Fig. 7D). Consistently, the after/before ratio with Yoda1 addition was significantly higher ($P < 0.001$) only when compared to DMSO in each group (Fig. 7G). The maximum upstroke velocity of HL-1 cell action potential had decreased significantly ($P < 0.001$) after Yoda1 addition in both control and flufenamic acid-treated groups, but no significant difference ($P = 0.277$) was found between the two groups (Fig. 7E). Accordingly, the after/before ratio with Yoda1 addition was significantly lower ($P < 0.001$) compared to DMSO addition in both groups (Fig. 7H).

For completeness, in Fast ISAP cells, DMSO addition showed no significant effect on action potential frequency (Fig. 8A). By contrast to Slow ISAP cells, Yoda1 addition (final concentration = 2 μM) induced a significant decrease in frequency ($P < 0.001$) in both control and flufenamic acid-treated groups (Fig. 8A). However, the frequency in the flufenamic acid-treated group was 43.0% higher ($P = 0.017$) than that in the control group after Yoda1 addition (Fig. 8A). Accordingly, the after/before ratio with Yoda1 addition is significantly lower ($P < 0.001$) than that with DMSO addition in both groups (Fig. 8B). Also, with Yoda1 addition, the flufenamic acid-treated group showed a 36.3% lesser decrease ($P = 0.011$) in after/before ratio than that in the control group (Fig. 8B). Because increased K^+ channel activity may cause slowing in action potential frequency (Tsantoulas & McMahon, 2014), we tested the selective BK channel opener NS 1619 (Olesen et al., 1994). As shown in Fig. 8A, the addition of NS 1619 (final concentration = 10 μM) induced a significant decrease ($P = 0.023$) in action potential frequency in the control group. Also, the after/before ratio with NS 1619 addition was significantly lower ($P = 0.037$) compared to DMSO addition (Fig. 8B).

The action potential frequency in Fast ISAP groups was at a similar level to the contraction frequency in

the rabbit SAN tissue (Fig. 9A) observed in the present study. Similarly, Yoda1 incubation (20 μM) caused a decrease ($P = 0.006$) in contraction frequency in the rabbit SAN-CT tissue (Fig. 9B–D), with an average of 12.5% ($P = 0.003$) (Fig. 9E), whereas DMSO control had no effect (Fig. 9D and E).

Knockdown of TRPM4 affects Yoda1 induced changes in action potential frequency

With *Trpm4*-targeting siRNA-mediated gene knockdown, *Trpm4* mRNA expression level was reduced by 71% ($P < 0.001$) in HL-1 cells compared to the cells with control siRNA treatment (Fig. 10A). TRPM4 protein expression levels in *Trpm4*-targeting siRNA-treated cells were 55% lower than that in control siRNA-treated cells ($P < 0.001$) (Fig. 10B and C). For validation of the gene knockdown, no significant difference was found in the *Piezo1* ($P = 0.867$) and *Cacna1c* ($P = 0.236$) mRNA expression levels between the *Trpm4*-targeting siRNA-treated cells and the control cells (Fig. 10D and E).

When comparing the action potential in Slow ISAP cells from *Trpm4*-targeting siRNA-treated group and control siRNA-treated group, Yoda1 addition (final concentration = 2 μM) induced a significant increase in action potential frequency ($P < 0.001$) in both groups (Fig. 11A–C). Also, the frequency in *Trpm4*-targeting siRNA-treated group was 16.3% lower ($P < 0.001$) than that in the control group after Yoda1 addition (Fig. 11A–C). Accordingly, a significantly higher ($P < 0.001$) after/before ratio was found with Yoda1 addition compared to DMSO addition in both groups (Fig. 11F). Again, DMSO had no significant impact on action potential frequency, APD90 or maximum upstroke velocity (Fig. 11C–E). With Yoda1 addition, the after/before ratio in *Trpm4*-targeting siRNA-treated group was 24.4% lower ($P = 0.002$) than that in the control group (Fig. 11F). For the APD90, Yoda1 addition caused a significant increase ($P < 0.001$) in both groups. Also, the APD90 in the *Trpm4*-targeting siRNA-treated group was found to be higher ($P = 0.015$) than that in the control group after Yoda1 addition (Fig. 11D). The after/before ratio with Yoda1 addition was significantly higher ($P < 0.001$) than that with DMSO in each group, but it showed no significant difference ($P = 0.097$) between the two groups (Fig. 11G).

There was a significant decrease ($P < 0.001$) in maximum upstroke velocity after Yoda1 addition in both groups but there was no significant difference ($P = 0.860$) between the two groups (Fig. 11E). Yoda1 after/before ratio was significantly lower than DMSO after/before ratio in both the *Trpm4*-targeting siRNA-treated group ($P = 0.036$) and the control group ($P = 0.003$), but the Yoda1 after/before ratio was not significantly different ($P = 0.683$) between the two groups (Fig. 11H).

Figure 7. Effects of TRPM4 pharmacological inhibition on Yoda1 induced action potential changes in Slow ISAP cells

A and B, representative AP traces before and after Yoda1 addition (final concentration = 2 μM) in CTL (A) or FFA (B) treated HL-1 cells. AP frequency (C), APD90 (D) and AP maximum upstroke velocity (E) compared between the CTL and FFA groups. Results are presented as before-after drug addition. AP frequency ratio (F), APD90 ratio (G) and maximum upstroke velocity ratio (H) calculated as the after/before drug addition ratio. Results are presented as scatter plots with the mean \pm SD ($n = 22-28$ per group with DMSO addition; $n = 24-38$ per group with Yoda1 addition). n represents the number of wells in a 96 well plate.

Discussion

In the present study, we employed the HL-1 mouse atrial myocyte-like cell line as an *in vitro* model to investigate functional coupling between Piezo1 and TRPM4 channels. The HL-1 mouse atrial myocyte-like cell line exhibits phenotypic similarities to other cardiac muscle cells, as well as the ability to generate spontaneous action potentials and contractions (Claycomb et al., 1998; Hu et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2020; Sartiani et al., 2002; Son et al., 2016; White et al., 2004). In the present study, we compared *Trpm4* and *Piezo1* mRNA expression levels in HL-1 cells relative to mouse atrial cardiomyocytes, ventricular cardiomyocytes and cultured cardiac fibroblasts. Considering the appreciable amount of TRPM4 and Piezo1 expression levels, the HL-1 cell line is a highly suitable model for our *in vitro* experiments. Previously, a large diversity in the spontaneous contraction frequency of HL-1 cells was shown in different studies

(Claycomb, 2001; Liu et al., 2020; Sartiani et al., 2002; Uehara et al., 2017; Wells et al., 2019; Yang & Murray, 2011). The HL-1 cells used in the present study were initially classified by their ISAP frequency (No, Slow or Fast). We developed cell culture protocol to control the ISAP frequency. The Slow ISAP group was the main focus of the present study because the frequency range is similar to the original report from Claycomb (2001). We suspect that this variation in ISAP is related to the expression level of connexins forming gap junctions between the cytoplasm of two adjacent cells, which play an essential role in the propagation of electrical activity throughout the heart by mediating cell-cell communication (Dias et al., 2014; Kaese & Verheule, 2012; Lambiase & Tinker, 2015; Severs et al., 2001). Our immunostaining results indicate that the Cx43 expression levels on the cell membrane are significantly increasing from No ISAP to Slow ISAP, and then to Fast ISAP group, which suggests that Cx43 expression level/localization is a key factor affecting the ISAP frequency in HL-1 cells.

Previous studies have shown that approximately 30% of the HL-1 cells exhibit I_f as an underlying current of the action potential (Sartiani et al., 2002; Yang & Murray, 2011). Indeed, we observed strong depolarizations between beats consistent with I_f . The presence of I_f and the fact that the L-type Ca^{2+} channels are driving HL-1 cell action potentials suggest similarities in the molecular origins of the action potential between HL-1 cells and pacemaker cells from the SAN (Belardinelli et al., 1988; Denyer & Brown, 1990; Zhou & Lipsius, 1992). Because the present study focused on synchronous action potentials and analysed the mean value of multiple cells, the I_f was not investigated specifically. In addition, the conduction velocity of HL-1 cells was investigated to further improve the data acquisition and analysis accuracy in genetic inhibition experimental groups. The HL-1 cell conduction velocity in Slow and Fast ISAP groups had no significant difference and was within a range from 10.07 to 34.23 $\mu\text{m ms}^{-1}$, which is relatively close to the conduction velocity in primary pacemaker tissue of mouse SAN (50–65 $\mu\text{m ms}^{-1}$) (Verheijck, 2001) compared to mouse atrial or ventricular conduction velocity (300–600 $\mu\text{m ms}^{-1}$) (Alcoléa et al., 2004; Kaese & Verheule, 2012; Thomas et al., 1998; van Veen et al., 2005).

In the present study, our electrophysiology data shows that acute stretch can activate Piezo1 currents in HL-1 cells. Also, Ca^{2+} induces TRPM4 currents, which can be inhibited by 50 μM flufenamic acid. Then, we used Yoda1 (Syeda et al., 2015) to chemically activate Piezo1 channels as a surrogate for mechanical stretch. Yoda1 addition (final concentration = 2 μM) induced increases in intracellular Ca^{2+} in HL-1 cells and initiated trains of action potentials (except for some 9-phenanthrol treated cells). This was especially obvious in cells that

Figure 8. Effects of TRPM4 pharmacological inhibition in Fast ISAP HL-1 cells

A, HL-1 cell AP frequency was compared among CTL and FFA groups. Results are presented as before-after drug addition. B, AP frequency ratio was calculated as after/before drug addition. Results are presented as scatter plots with the mean \pm SD ($n = 11-15$ per group with DMSO addition; $n = 7-18$ per group with Yoda1 addition). n represents the number of wells in a 96 well plate.

Figure 9. Effect of Yoda1 on beating frequency of rabbit sinoatrial node (SAN) and crista terminalis (CT) tissue

A, images of both atria before SAN-CT excision (left), once attached to triangles (middle) and in the recording chamber (right). B and C, representative recordings showing force of contractions and used to calculate contraction frequency before (B) and after (C) 15 min of incubation with Yoda1 (20 μ M). D, contraction frequency in both DMSO and Yoda1 addition groups. Results are presented as before-after 15 min drug incubation. E, frequency change is expressed as a percentage relative to before drug incubation ($n = 3$ samples from three rabbits in the DMSO incubation group; $n = 13$ samples from six rabbits in the Yoda1 incubation group (multiple samples could be obtained from on SAN-CT). All recordings were performed at 37°C.

showed no initial spontaneous activity (No ISAP group). Also, in Slow ISAP groups, Yoda1 addition induced a significant increase in the action potential frequency and APD90 and a decrease in maximum upstroke velocity. By contrast, in Fast ISAP groups, Yoda1 addition decreases the action potential frequency. Because Yoda1 is a specific Piezo1 agonist (Syeda et al., 2015), the effect induced by Yoda1 addition is a result of Piezo1 activation, especially when DMSO addition showed no effect. In addition, with Slow ISAP cells, a reduced effect of Yoda1 on action potential frequency in the siRNA-mediated *Piezo1* gene knockdown group supports a Piezo1-specific effect. The *Piezo1*-knockdown group showed a prolongation of APD90 at baseline compared to the control groups. One possible mechanism is that the reduction of Piezo1 expression caused less Ca^{2+} entry into the cells, which may affect Ca^{2+} activated K^+ channels, such as the large (BK), intermediate (IK) or small conductance Ca^{2+} activated K^+ (SK) channels. The reduced activity of the BK, IK or SK channels might then explain the prolongation of APD90 as a result of the reduced repolarizing current (Imlach et al., 2010; Jakob et al., 2021; Jeevaratnam et al., 2018; Surawicz,

1992; Takahashi & Naruse, 2012; Weisbrod, 2020; Yang & Murray, 2011). Indeed, previous work has both linked Piezo1 to BK channel activation (Jakob et al., 2021) and linked BK channel function to the regulation of heart rate (Pineda et al., 2021). Interestingly, our *ex vivo* studies in rabbit SANs show that Yoda1 reduces the frequency of AP generation consistent with our HL-1 results from the fast ISAP cells. This perhaps hints at a functional role for Piezo1 channels in the SAN. The APD90 prolongation in the *Piezo1*-knockdown group after Yoda1 addition was probably a result of its higher baseline because there was no significant difference between the control and the *Piezo1*-knockdown groups in the after/before ratio.

For pharmacological inhibition of TRPM4, we incubated HL-1 cells with flufenamic acid (Constantine et al., 2016; Guinamard et al., 2006; Simard et al., 2013; Ullrich et al., 2005). We focussed on flufenamic acid because of the non-specific effects we identified with the other commonly used TRPM4 blocker 9-phenanthrol, which we found also blocks Piezo1 channels in the present study. Flufenamic acid (20 μM) reduced the increase in frequency after Yoda1 addition by more than 30% in

Figure 10. Validation of the *Trpm4* gene knockdown

A, relative *Trpm4* mRNA expression in HL-1 cells treated with *Trpm4*-targeting siRNA (si*Trpm4*) or its control siRNA (siCTL) ($n = 4$ per group). **B**, western blots showing TRPM4 protein expression in HL-1 cells treated with siCTL or si*Trpm4*. **C**, TRPM4 protein expression quantitative data normalized by GAPDH ($n = 5$ per group). **D** and **E**, *Piezo1* (**D**) and *Cacna1c* (**E**) mRNA expression in si*Trpm4*-treated and siCTL-treated HL-1 cells ($n = 4$ per group). In all panels, quantitative results are presented as scatter plots with the mean \pm SD. Fold change was calculated relative to corresponding siCTL group. n represents the number of separate culture dishes.

Figure 11. Effects of TRPM4 knockdown on Yoda1 induced action potential changes in Slow ISAP cells
 A and B, representative action potential (AP) traces before and after Yoda1 addition (final concentration = 2 μ M) in siCTL (A) or siTrpm4 (B) treated HL-1 cells. AP frequency (C), APD90 (D) and AP maximum upstroke velocity (E)

compared between siCTL-treated and si*Trpm4*-treated groups. Results are presented as before-after drug addition. AP frequency ratio (*F*), APD90 ratio (*G*) and AP maximum upstroke velocity ratio (*H*) calculated by after/before drug addition. Results are presented as scatter plots with the mean \pm SD ($n = 22-26$ per group with DMSO addition; $n = 24-35$ per group with Yoda1 addition). n represents the number of wells in a 96 well plate.

the No ISAP and Slow ISAP groups, and reduced the decrease in frequency after Yoda1 addition by 36.3% in the Fast ISAP group. Although flufenamic acid may also block other channels such as Ca^{2+} -activated Cl^- channels (Guinamard et al., 2013; Gwanyanya et al., 2010), the flufenamic acid effect in the present study most probably reflects the TRPM4 effect on action potential because TRPM4 is more sensitive than other channels to flufenamic acid at the concentration used in the present study (Guinamard et al., 2013; Simard et al., 2013). The TRPM4 effect on Slow ISAP cells was further confirmed using TRPM4 knockdown. siRNA-mediated *Trpm4* knockdown led to a 24.4% lesser increase in frequency after Yoda1 addition. This result is strong evidence supporting Piezo1-mediated activation of TRPM4 in HL-1 cells, consistent with the pharmacological inhibition.

Similar to the mechanisms discussed in our previous studies (Guo et al., 2021; Yu et al., 2022), when stimulated by the local Ca^{2+} influx through Yoda1-evoked Piezo1 activation, TRPM4 could depolarize the plasma membrane to further stimulate other Ca^{2+} -permeable channels such as the L-type and T-type Ca^{2+} channels (Abriel et al., 2012; Hof et al., 2019; Launay et al., 2002). Indeed, we identified that L-type Ca^{2+} channels are indispensable for action potential generation in HL-1 cells. TRPM4 activity could also induce reverse activity of the $\text{Na}^+/\text{Ca}^{2+}$ exchanger through local Na^+ loading (Conway, 2001; Wang et al., 2018), leading to a further increase of local Ca^{2+} . The increase in APD90 and decrease in maximum upstroke velocity after Yoda1 addition might be related to the effects of intracellular Ca^{2+} concentration on NCX (Eisner et al., 2009). Increase of Ca^{2+} efflux and Na^+ influx by the electrogenic NCX can result in an increased net inward current from NCX activity, which could cause prolongation of action potential duration and lower upstroke velocity (Barceñas-Ruiz et al., 1987; Eisner et al., 2009). Although not the main result, the situation is more complicated in Fast ISAP groups with higher basal Ca^{2+} concentrations. As mentioned, similar results were found in our *ex vivo* rabbit SAN experiments. The Fast ISAP cell action potential and the rabbit SAN tissue contraction had similar basal frequencies, which decreased by Yoda1 addition. One possible mechanism is that the increased intracellular Ca^{2+} from Piezo1 activation has to reach a certain level to activate other ion channels such as BK (Jakob et al., 2021; Takahashi & Naruse, 2012) and/or cause local Ca^{2+} overload. Studies have identified BK channels as contributing factors to the regulation of the

heart rate (Imlach et al., 2010; Peyronnet et al., 2016; Takahashi & Naruse, 2012). In the present study, the selective BK channel opener NS 1619 (Olesen et al., 1994) induced a decrease in action potential frequency in the Fast ISAP group, which is a similar trend to the cells with Yoda1-evoked Piezo1 activation. This decrease in frequency is probably an effect of BK activation because increased K^+ channel activity may cause slowing in action potential frequency (Tsantoulas & McMahon, 2014). Follow-up studies are required to investigate these observations further.

TRPM4 has been shown to influence the waveform and frequency of the cardiac action potential. Hof et al. (2013) reported that inhibition of TRPM4 by 9-phenanthrol causes decrease in action potential frequency in mouse right atrium, rat right atrium and rabbit SAN. Simard et al. (2013) showed shortening in atrial action potential duration in a TRPM4 global knockout mouse or with flufenamic acid treatment. Also, 9-phenanthrol can cause shortening in action potential duration in AngII-treated HL-1 cells (Hu et al., 2017). In the present study, either flufenamic acid or siRNA-mediated *Trpm4* knockdown did not affect the baseline values in action potential frequency, APD90 and maximum upstroke velocity. The TRPM4 effect on action potential frequency was only shown when Piezo1 was activated by Yoda1 addition. Although there was no significant difference in baselines, the subtle gap in baseline probably causes APD90 difference between the *Trpm4*-knockdown group and the control group because no significant difference was found in the after/before ratio. In addition, the HL-1 action potential data in the present study shows that 9-phenanthrol blocks Yoda1-evoked Piezo1 action potential within a similar concentration range compared to other studies. This result is supported by our HL-1 cell Ca^{2+} data and is consistent with our HEK293T cell electrophysiology data, which showed that 30 min incubations with 9-phenanthrol blocked stretch-activated Piezo1 currents. Consequently, 9-phenanthrol was excluded from the main experiments. Given the off-target effects of 9-phenanthrol (Garland et al., 2015) existing studies implicating TRPM4 using 9-phenanthrol might need to be revisited.

One limitation of the present study is that *Trpm4*- or *Piezo1*-targeting siRNA did not achieve complete gene knockdown in HL-1 cells. The TRPM4 protein in siRNA-treated cells was at a similar level to the study by Hu et al. (2017) using the same siRNA product (catalog, no. MSS229248; Invitrogen). Nevertheless, in the present

study, the effect of *Trpm4* or *Piezo1* deficiency was clearly shown in action potential frequency change after Yoda1 addition.

In summary, in the present study, *Piezo1* and *Trpm4* gene expression levels in HL-1 cells were compared to mouse atrial cardiomyocytes, ventricular cardiomyocytes and cardiac fibroblasts. We developed a robust protocol to generate HL-1 cell monolayers with varying degrees of excitability. We also demonstrated that the action potential frequency in HL-1 cells was correlated with changes in Cx43 expression levels and localization. Of most importance, however, the present study provides the first direct evidence of a functional interaction between *Piezo1* and TRPM4 in a cardiomyocyte-like cell line. When *Piezo1* is activated, TRPM4 is stimulated by the resulting increase of intracellular Ca^{2+} which causes an increase in action potential frequency in HL-1 cells. This model in which a Ca^{2+} -activated ion channel acts as a downstream effector or amplifier of a primary mechanosensitive current is probably ubiquitous within mechanosensory pathways.

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Additional information

Data availability statement

The data generated or analysed during the present study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

Author contributions

Y.G., D.C., Z.-Y.Y., T.S., A.Y.C., R.P. and C.D.C. were responsible for data curation. Y.G., D.C., T.S., A.P.H., R.P. and C.D.C. were responsible for formal analysis. Y.G., Z.-Y.Y., A.Y.C., A.P.H., R.P. and C.D.C. were responsible for validation. Y.G., D.C., Z.-Y.Y., T.S. and C.D.C. were responsible for investigation. Y.G., D.C., T.S. and C.D.C. were responsible for visualization. Y.G., D.C., T.S., A.Y.C., A.P.H., R.P. and C.D.C. were responsible for methodology. Y.G., T.S. and C.D.C. were responsible for writing the original draft. Z.-Y.Y., R.P., M.P.F., C.D.C. and B.M. were responsible for supervision. R.P., M.P.F., C.D.C. and B.M. were responsible for resources. B.M. was responsible for study conceptualization.

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Supporting information

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of the HTML view of the article. Supporting information files available:

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